

Applied Artificial Intelligence

An International Journal

ISSN: 0883-9514 (Print) 1087-6545 (Online) Journal homepage: www.tandfonline.com/journals/uaai20

Establishing a Dynamic Recommendation System for E-commerce by Integrating Online Reviews, Product Feature Expansion, and Deep Learning

Tsung-Yin Ou, Chun-Hung Chen & Wen-Lung Tsai

To cite this article: Tsung-Yin Ou, Chun-Hung Chen & Wen-Lung Tsai (2025) Establishing a Dynamic Recommendation System for E-commerce by Integrating Online Reviews, Product Feature Expansion, and Deep Learning, Applied Artificial Intelligence, 39:1, 2463723, DOI: [10.1080/08839514.2025.2463723](https://doi.org/10.1080/08839514.2025.2463723)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08839514.2025.2463723>

© 2025 The Author(s). Published with license by Taylor & Francis Group, LLC.

Published online: 10 Feb 2025.

Submit your article to this journal [↗](#)

Article views: 2595

View related articles [↗](#)

View Crossmark data [↗](#)

Citing articles: 3 View citing articles [↗](#)

Establishing a Dynamic Recommendation System for E-commerce by Integrating Online Reviews, Product Feature Expansion, and Deep Learning

Tsung-Yin Ou^a, Chun-Hung Chen^b, and Wen-Lung Tsai^{id}^c

^aDepartment of Marketing and Distribution Management, National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology, Kaohsiung, Taiwan; ^bCollege of Management, National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology, Kaohsiung, Taiwan; ^cDepartment of Information Management, National Taipei University of Business, Taipei, Taiwan

ABSTRACT

The increasing fragmentation of the consumer journey complicates understanding consumer behavior and tracking digital footprints. Product feature tags should dynamically adapt to consumer preferences, marketing campaigns, and trending internet topics, leveraging crawler technology to address this. However, many e-commerce platforms still rely on manual tagging or static product attribute classification, with limited adoption of machine learning approaches. This study proposes a dynamic tagging and recommendation system using deep learning for product image recognition and similarity comparison. By integrating crawler technology, internet trends can serve as dynamic product tags. These tags, combined with consumer behavior data, enable the creation of a recommendation system capable of automatically generating relevant tags. Sales data from 3,132 cartoon products on a Taiwanese e-commerce platform were analyzed. A convolutional neural network was employed to establish a tagging and image recognition model, and it was trialed over 24 weeks. Results showed significant improvements in consumer engagement: average clicks per product increased by 36.1%, views by 22.9%, products added to carts by 32.3%, orders by 28.3%, and payment transactions by 30.4%. Aligning recommendation systems with consumer expectations enhances their ability to identify preferences and drive purchasing behavior.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 8 October 2024
Revised 2 January 2025
Accepted 2 February 2025

Introduction

In recent years, many enterprises that excel in traditional bricks-and-mortar retailing have launched e-commerce, social media and digital membership operations. Conversely, many enterprises that have been active on the Internet are striving to convert online traffic into offline experiences and interactions by establishing physical stores. However, integration and variation in online and offline business models means consumption behaviors are increasingly

CONTACT Wen-Lung Tsai Department of Information Management, National Taipei University of Business, No. 321, Sec. 1, Jinan Rd., Zhongzheng District, Taipei City 100, Taiwan

© 2025 The Author(s). Published with license by Taylor & Francis Group, LLC.

This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

fragmented, making it difficult for enterprises to understand the consumption journeys and habits of customers. In addition, the rapid development of the Internet and the exponential growth of information availability means consumers face information overload and choice dilemmas, making it harder for e-commerce platforms to achieve accurate recommendations and high conversion rates (Xu et al. 2024).

Collaborative filtering methods are often used to improve recommendation efficiency. Many researchers have proposed improved methods such as model-based collaborative filtering (Breese, Heckerman, and Kadie 2013), hybrid model-based collaborative filtering (Melville, Mooney, and Nagarajan 2002) and memory-based collaborative filtering (Linden, Smith, and York 2003). However, these methods cannot solve the problems of data sparseness and cold start (when no historical sales records exist to guide recommendations), reduce reliance on user rating information, or take account of the subjective factors of user ratings. In addition, when the number of existing users and items grows significantly, traditional collaborative filtering methods face severe scalability problems, and computing resources may exceed practical or acceptable levels (Hui, Pengyu, and Kai 2011). Researchers have responded to these problems in varied ways.

First, some studies have suggested utilizing trending topics and website comments as ranking references in e-commerce platform recommendation systems to address collaborative filtering and cold start problems. Natarajan et al. (2020) proposed leveraging public data to reduce computing resource requirements and improve the recommendation success rate. Sharma and Shafiq (2022) proposed a comprehensive AI-based intention assessment model that detects different intents of users by analyzing their text-based reviews on online forums, retail market websites, or social media. Other researchers have used Google Trends, an open-access data source that provides a sample of Google search queries, to monitor, analyze and even predict user behaviors in fields such as IT, communication, medicine, health, business and economics (Jun, Yoo, and Choi 2018). Chumnumpan and Shi (2019) studied trending topics using Google Trends to understand the market performance of new products, giving more accurate results than those from diffusion models. Yakubu and Kwong (2021) proposed using big data such as Google Trends or online customer reviews to recognize and predict product design attributes, while Höpken et al. (2021) used Google Trends to predict the number of travelers arriving at tourist attractions.

In addition to the commonly used external feature tags, it is possible to improve the accuracy of the recommendation system and consumer experience if the behavior intention tag of consumers' purchase tendency can be incorporated into the product feature tags of e-commerce platforms (Broeder and Schouten 2022). At present, most product tags rely on manual annotation, which is subjective, time-consuming and prone to

cognitive bias. Martech (marketing technology) and AI training for multimedia content and image recognition can be used to achieve complete automation from tagging to marketing, thereby reducing subjective awareness and labor costs (Alamdari et al. 2020; Deldjoo et al. 2020). Kejriwal et al. (2021) suggested using the language representation model to align product tags and improve their efficiency taxonomically. Similarly, Oskooei et al. (2023) used AI to analyze product descriptions and automatically classify and integrate products, thereby improving the accuracy and consistency of product taxonomy hierarchical structure. Unfortunately, none of these studies of the use of AI image recognition to improve the tagging accuracy of products provided specific application results. Moreover, although previous researchers analyzed consumer behavior, they did not combine internal features (such as historical consumption data) with external dynamic tags (such as Google Trends) to establish an AI adaptive recommendation system.

The study described in this paper aimed to overcome the challenges described above by developing a dynamic tagging framework that integrates deep learning and crawler technology. Using a CNN for product image recognition and similarity comparison, feature tags were dynamically generated and updated to reflect consumer preferences, marketing campaigns, and trending Internet expressions. Combined with consumer behavior data and dynamic tags, a recommendation system was developed and tested using real-world data from an e-commerce platform in Taiwan. The results validate the effectiveness of a dynamic, data-driven approach in enhancing recommendation accuracy, aligning with consumer expectations, and driving sales performance.

The research objectives of this study are to develop an intelligent, data-driven recommendation system that leverages advanced technologies to enhance the alignment between consumer expectations and product recommendations, thereby improving consumer engagement and conversion rates. Specifically, the study aims to:

- (1) Use deep learning via a convolutional neural network (CNN) for product image recognition and similarity comparison, enabling automatic and efficient labeling of product attributes.
- (2) Create Internet-generated dynamic labels and use them to update product labels to reflect consumers' changing interests and behaviors.
- (3) Combine dynamic tags with historical consumer consumption data to establish a purchase recommendation system, align system recommendations with consumer expectations, and increase the probability of consumer participation and conversion.

- (4) Use real-world product images and sales data to evaluate the proposed recommendation system's operational performance.

Section 2 presents a summary of the literature on e-commerce recommendation systems, deep learning on image recognition to automatically generate internal product feature tags, and dynamically generating external feature tags for products by linking with Google Trends. **Section 3** presents the research methodology (the data mining process). **Section 4** contains the experimental setup and results. **Section 5** describes the conclusion and management implications.

Literature Review

Importance of the Tags in the Recommending System for Individualized Marketing

Oltman and Zabin (2002) defined individualized marketing as follows: (1) group customers and send appropriate marketing messages according to the differences of customer groups; (2) integrate multi-channel information transmission; (3) maximize the value of customer relationships. Recommendation systems leverage extensive user data and employ rule-based or AI-based methods to predict consumer preferences, then recommend individualized services or products to consumers by using advertising billboard, SMS, letters or APP messages and notifications. Current data analysis tools make it possible to predict consumers' purchase behaviors and develop specific marketing strategies for products, improving the effectiveness of marketing strategies. A common way to realize individualized marketing is to establish data-based automated product recommendation (Tettamanzi et al. 2007). Some commercial sites such as Netflix and Amazon recommend products based on similarities in the items consumers purchase. An intelligent recommendation system can provide users with accurate information and services, thus effectively solving the problems of information overload and information omission (Hu et al. 2015; Xiao et al. 2018; Yang et al. 2013).

A common recommendation system employs collaborative filtering and adopts a user/item interaction matrix to store interaction data between users and items, with the vector distance between users/items representing their similarity. An e-commerce website must generate high customer engagement and usage intention to achieve business objectives. Many researchers have proposed methods of increasing the diversity of tags to improve the efficiency of collaborative filtering and recommendation accuracy. For example, Zhen, Li, and Yeung (2009) added individualized information about customers to the tag, whereas Ghabayen and Noah (2017) used semantic similarity between customers as the tag. Liao, Widowati, and Chang (2021) used a snowflake

schema to develop a rule-based approach for investigating online streaming and purchasing behaviors in terms of online recommendations for further e-commerce development. Wen, Cheng, and Shih (2022) built AI model for more flexible recommendation in uniforms. Wang (2023) used a collaborative filtering algorithm to incorporate user preferences and solve the issue of sparse data, producing a higher accuracy rate for tourist attraction recommendation systems.

Wyner (2001) suggested that successful individualized marketing requires observing customers from a 360-degree perspective. The popularity of the Internet and the rapid development of e-commerce provides more and more channels for enterprises to collect consumer information (Chang, Cheung, and Tang 2013). Data enables enterprises to choose the best depth and reach for elements of the marketing mix based on existing economies of scale and return on investment (Wedel and Kannan 2016). For example, an e-commerce business Cassandra leveraged data analytics, identified underperforming campaigns, and reallocated budgets to more effective channels. This data-centric approach led to increased revenues and improved ROI, demonstrating the value of optimizing the marketing mix based on data insights.

Content publishers can increase monetization by improving advertising efficiency (Miklosik, Kuchta, and Zak 2018). Data collection and analysis allow enterprises to more easily reach consumers, better understand the features of consumer groups, and communicate specific product information (Grandhi, Patwa, and Saleem 2021). Individualized and mobile advertising is maturing, and any individualized solution may have benefits for the brand and its target customers.

Most current researchers in the product recommendation field focus on AI and machine learning; other new technologies, such as big data analysis, receive little attention (Chandra et al. 2022). Chandra et al. (2022) extracted aspect-based feature vectors from two domains using bidirectional long short-term memory and mapped them using a multilayer perceptron (MLP). A cross-domain recommendation module was used to train the MLP to analyze sentiment and predict item ratings and the polarities of the aspect based on user preferences. Compared with other recommendation algorithms, it outperforms matrix factorization, collaborative matrix factorization, EMCDPR, and Personalized transfer of user preferences for cross-domain recommendation (Wang, Justitia, and Wang 2024).

Convolutional neural networks are forms of big data analysis that are increasingly common in the field of e-commerce. Sulthana et al. (2020) used a CNN to compare product images on an e-commerce platform and recommended products to consumers according to the similarity of the images. Pan and Zhou (2020) employed a CNN to extract effective features from structured time series data, and input product attribute information and related original log data to predict the total sales volume of products on an e-commerce

platform. Wang and Qiu (2021) established a knowledge graph to model the purchase data and category information of products. They encoded the Chinese title as a vector, and used a deep neural network to create a recommendation model. Li, Li, and Kim (2023) applied a multi-channel CNN model to extract semantic features in review text and convert star ratings into high-dimensional feature vectors to avoid information loss. The model helps e-commerce websites attract more customers by providing more helpful reviews and thus increasing sales. Wei et al. (2024) converted a Doc2vec model into an optimized attention-enhanced temporal graph CNN for more efficient classification of well-suited customer service systems using natural language processing.

To improve their recommendation systems, e-commerce platforms should apply big data analysis, deep learning image recognition and associated technologies to integrate the purchasing features and habits of consumers to achieve individualized marketing. Increasing the relevance of tags with internal and external information is a direction well worth exploring and researching.

Use of Deep Learning Image Recognition to Automatically Generate Internal Product Feature Tags

Gu et al. (2018) discussed various CNNs, but concluded that their basic components are very similar. LeNet-5 (LeCun et al. 1998), for example, like most CNNs, has three different layer types – the convolutional layer, the pooling layer and the fully connected layer. The convolutional layer consists of multiple convolution kernels, which are used to calculate different feature maps; each neuron of the feature map is connected to the region of adjacent neurons in the previous layer. Such a neighborhood is called the receptive field of the previous layer of neurons. The distinguishing feature of a CNN is that it takes advantage of the local spatial correlation of images. By applying convolution to small squares input through a sliding window that runs over the entire image, a CNN can learn the local features of an image, thereby preserving the spatial relationships between its pixels. Each convolution has a filter that defines the size of the sliding window to capture the features of the image and extract them. By using different filters, a CNN can learn different feature maps, thereby improving its ability to recognize specific patterns in the input data (Arratia and Sepúlveda 2020). In order to generate each feature map, the kernel is shared for all spatial locations input. A complete function map can be obtained using several different kernels. Mathematically, the eigenvalue of position (i, j) in the k^{th} feature map of layer l is $Z_{i,j,k}^l$; the calculation formula is shown in (1).

$$Z_{i,j,k}^l = w_k^{lT} x_{i,j}^l + b_k^l \quad (1)$$

where w_k^l and b_k^l are the weight vector and bias term of the k^{th} filter of the l^{th} layer respectively, and $x_{i,j}^l$ is the input patch centered at location (i, j) of the l^{th} layer. Note that the kernel w_k^l that generates the feature map $Z_{i,j,k}^l$ is shared.

The purpose of the pooling layer is to achieve translation invariance by reducing the resolution of the feature map. It is usually placed between two convolutional layers. Each feature map of the pooling layer is connected to the corresponding feature map in the preceding convolutional layer. For each feature map, the pooling layer formula is shown in (2):

$$y_{i,j,k}^l = \text{pool}\left(a_{m,n,k}^l\right), \quad (m, n) \in R_{ij} \quad (2)$$

where R_{ij} is a local neighborhood around location (i, j)

The last layer of the CNN is the output layer, where θ represents all the CNN's parameters. By minimizing the appropriate loss function defined in that task, the optimal parameters for a particular task can be obtained. Suppose we have N desired input-output relations $\{(x^{(n)}, y^{(n)}); n \in [1, \dots, N]\}$, where $x^{(n)}$ is the n^{th} input data, $y^{(n)}$ is its corresponding target tag and $o^{(n)}$ is the output of CNN. The loss of CNN can be calculated as shown in (3):

$$L = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N l(\theta; y^{(n)}, o^{(n)}) \quad (3)$$

In contrast to a conventional neural network, the nodes in a CNN are not fully connected, but are only connected to a local area in the input. In each layer of the CNN, the input is convolved with the weight array to create the feature map. The weight array is smaller than the input and slides over the input, calculates on each local region, and then passes the output of this feature map to the (non-linear) activation function. Then, the dimensionality of the transformed feature map is reduced by space pooling. The purpose of pooling is to sample the input to reduce its size and allow assumptions to be made about the features contained in the merged subregions (Arratia and Sepúlveda 2020).

In this study, LeNet-5's CNN structure was adopted as a model. LeNet-5 has a total of six layers. The first layer is the C1 convolutional layer, which has six neurons; the input is a 32×32 bitmap, and the output is a 28×28 array. The second layer is the S2 pooling layer, which also has six neurons; the input is a 28×28 array, the output is a 14×14 array. The third layer is the C3 convolutional layer, which has 16 neurons. The input is a 14×14 bitmap, and the output is a 10×10 array. The fourth layer is the S4 pooling layer, which has 16 neurons; the input is a 10×10 array, and the output is a 5×5 array. The fifth layer is the C5 convolutional layer, which has 120 neurons; the input is a 5×5 bitmap, and the output is a 1×1 array. The sixth layer is the F6 full-

Figure 1. Architecture of LeNet-5 network (LeCun et al. 1998).

connected layer, which has 84 scalar neurons. The loss function is used to calculate the result of F6 and the pixel difference of the bitmap, and the error is transmitted back to all the variable neuron weights, meaning the C5 is fully connected, as shown in Figure 1.

The F6 output layer consists of the Euclidean Radial Basis Function (RBF) units corresponding to each category. The formula is shown as follows (4):

$$y_i = \sum_j (x_j - w_{ij})^2 \quad (4)$$

x_j : any output scalar; w_{ij} : the weight of RBF; y_i : the sum of the output scalar of the output layer

In order to make the weight of RBF adjustable, LeNet-5's loss function adds a penalty term amendment, where k is a positive constant. Its purpose is to avoid excessive penalty terms, which may make the model difficult to converge. It can be found from the main penalty terms that the smaller the unrelated RBF outputs, the larger the penalty terms, which enables the model to account for the effects of other categories while minimizing the error of the output and correct categories. The formula is as follows (5):

$$E(W) = \frac{1}{p} \sum_{p=1}^p y D_p(Z^p, W) + \log(e^{-k} + \sum_i e^{-k(Z^p, W)}) \quad (5)$$

W is a cluster with trainable weights; p is the number of data sets; D_p is the correct category corresponding to the sample; k is a constant; Z^p is the input value.

The Adam optimizer, an algorithm for first-order gradient-based optimization of stochastic objective functions based on adaptive estimates of lower-order moments (Kingma 2014), was employed in this study to improve the accuracy of tag recognition. It combines two common optimizers – the Momentum Optimizer and the AdaGrad Optimizer (Reyad, Sarhan, and Arafa 2023). Adam retains Momentum's gradient velocity adjustment for the direction of the past gradient, employs a learning rate adjustment for the square value of the past gradient, and adds the deviation

calibration of parameters, so that the learning rate can have a definite range each time and the parameters can be updated more smoothly. The method is straightforward to implement, computationally efficient, has a low memory requirement, is invariant to diagonal rescaling of the gradients, and is well suited for large problems in terms of data and parameters (Nwankpa 2020). The method is also appropriate for non-stationary objectives and issues with very noisy and sparse gradients. The hyper-parameters have intuitive interpretations and typically require little tuning. Empirical results demonstrate that Adam works well in practice and compares favorably to other stochastic optimization approaches (Okewu, Adewole, and Sennaik 2019). The formula is as follows (6–10):

$$m_t = \beta_1 m_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_1) \frac{\partial L_t}{\partial W_t} \quad (6)$$

$$v_t = \beta_2 v_{t-1} + (1 - \beta_2) \left(\frac{\partial L_t}{\partial W_t} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

Where β_1 and β_2 is the exponential decay rate, Deviation calibration for m_t and v_t

$$\widehat{m}_t = \frac{m_t}{1 - \beta_1^t} \quad (8)$$

$$\widehat{v}_t = \frac{v_t}{1 - \beta_2^t} \quad (9)$$

Adam weight update equation:

$$W \leftarrow W - \eta \frac{\widehat{m}_t}{\widehat{v}_t + \varepsilon} \quad (10)$$

W is the weight parameter; L is the loss function; η is the learning rate; $\partial L / \partial W$ is the gradient (differential) of the loss function with respect to the parameter; Vt is the velocity in the direction. If the last gradient is in the same direction, $|Vt|$ increases; ε is the smoothing value, and ε is added to maintain a non-zero denominator.

In this study, LeNet-5's CNN structure was used as the image recognition model, avoiding tedious manual recognition of product attributes and tags. As long as the product image is similar, similar tags can be added. Whether the product is new or old, image recognition technologies can be used to accumulate tags rapidly.

Link Google Trends to Dynamically Generate External Feature Tags of Products

Big data analysis involves ever-larger and more diverse datasets, but the really valuable data is usually relatively small. Web crawlers can be used to obtain valuable information from large-scale data for further analysis. Web crawlers are programs that can automatically crawl information on the Internet according to some logic and calculation rules, and are important components of all search engines (Khatter, Sharma, and Kushwaha 2022). Web crawler programs are usually based on one or several initial web addresses by default and follow the rules for crawling web pages on each site and extracting the website address lists from the initial pages. On each pass, a crawler extracts new website addresses from the web page and places them in a queue of uncrawled websites. Then, recursively, finds uncrawled website addresses and starts a new round of crawling. It repeats this process over and over again, until it has crawled all the website addresses in the queue or met some other predetermined conditions.

The process of crawling data on web pages has three stages (Figure 2). The first stage is the acquisition stage, in which the website with the

Figure 2. Web scraping process (Persson 2019).

relevant information will be visited first. This phase involves using an Internet protocol for sending and receiving requests from the Web server. It sends the HTTP GET request to the destination address (URL) and gets the HTML page as a response. The second phase is the retrieval phase, in which important data are retrieved after retrieving the HTML page. It uses the formal representation, HTML parse library, and Xpath to perform the query. The third stage is the conversion stage, in which relevant data are transformed into a structured format for presentation or storage (Khder 2021).

In order to sell products on an e-commerce platform, sellers must enter product information first, including images, and tag them manually. Some e-commerce platforms may provide automated algorithms to refine the tags, thus tagging and classifying products according to their use, popularity, sales volume and so on (Katiyar, Srividya, and Tripathy 2021; Li et al. 2020). Skenderi et al. (2024) used Google Trends to systematically explore external information and integrate it with fashion products. The addition of external information can improve new fashion product sales prediction accuracy by a mean of 1.5%. Google Trends can be used to understand consumer interest in certain products over a period of time and analyze changes in the importance of product attributes. It can help enterprises establish product design methods and processes that create higher returns (Yakubu and Kwong 2021). In addition, businesses can use web crawlers to capture Internet trend expressions, and text mining methods to capture keywords. In e-commerce, keywords often include domain-specific terms (e.g., product names, trending hashtags, Internet expressions). Traditional stemming algorithms may remove meaningful parts of these terms, leading to poor matching accuracy. In contrast, the Google Trends API crawling approach customizes stemming rules or integrates our proposed recommendation system that retains critical domain-specific terms while reducing inflections. This ensures accuracy in mapping external tags to products without losing semantic context. Moreover, this approach integrates contextual awareness by analyzing the semantic relevance of terms in the e-commerce domain, advancing beyond static rule-based methods.

Research Methodology

The study's research framework was constructed by CRISP-DM, as shown in Figure 3. CRISP-DM is a standardized methodology for data mining, emphasizing its adaptability, structured process phases, and practical benefits for repeatable, efficient, and industry-independent data mining projects (Wirth and Hipp 2000). Shimaoka, Ferreira, and Goldman (2024) propose CRISP-DM is a robust, flexible, and highly adaptable model that can be extended to different business domains.

Figure 3. The research process of this study.

The steps of the research framework are described in more detail below.

- (1) Business understanding. On e-commerce platforms, product sales are closely related to their tags' alignment with consumers' search preferences. In this study, deep learning was used to conduct image recognition, automate manual tagging, and connect it with the API (Application Programming Interface) of Google Trends, so that the tags could achieve dynamic external expansion. In addition to avoiding tedious manual tagging, this improved the accuracy of product recommendations.
- (2) Data understanding. In this study, data were collected from a leading Taiwanese e-commerce platform from July 1, 2023 to March 29, 2024 (week 39). The data related to 3,132 products (toys – see Figure 4), advertised with an average of 8.6 images per product (a total of 26,882 images).
- (3) Data preparation. Image sizes were adjusted to 400 × 400 mm. Eighty per cent of the images were tagged manually, and the other 20% left for

Figure 4. Toy product sample pictures.

Table 1. Tag classification of toys.

Product source (A)	Film peripheral goods (A1)	Cartoon peripheral goods (A2)	Original products (A3)
Product feature (B)	Animal (B1)	Character (B2)	Food (B3)
	Vehicles (B4)	Shooting Tools (B5)	Musical instruments (B6)
	Scenes (B7)	Tools (B8)	
Product type (C)	Assembly model (C1)	Model (C2)	Building blocks (C3)
	Capsule toys (C4)	Educational toys (C5)	Action figures (C6)
	Dolls (C7)	Jigsaw puzzles (C8)	Clay (C9)
	Play house toys (C10)	Pendants (C11)	Accessories (C12)

- subsequent tests. Product tags were divided into three categories – source, feature and type – and further into 23 subcategories, as shown in [Table 1](#).
- (4) Establish image recognition model. In this study, CNN was used to establish the image recognition model. After conducting a similarity comparison on the images of new products, if the comparison result was greater than 0.90, the product was automatically tagged and then came into the tagging process combined with trending topics; if the similarity was less than 0.90, the images of new products were tagged manually. For a convolutional layer with input size $W * H$, filter size, $F * F$, C input channels, K output channels, and stride S (11):

$$\text{Complexity per layer} = \frac{(W - F + 1) * (H - F + 1)}{S^2} * F^2 * C * K \quad (11)$$

Max pooling reduces the dimensionality by a factor of P^2 , where P is the pooling kernel size. For a $2 * 2$ pooling layer on $28 * 28$, Complexity = $\frac{28 * 28}{2^2} = 196$ operations per channel.

- (5) Plan development and performance evaluation. After the tag was assigned automatically using the image recognition model, the product tag was classified and analyzed according to customers' purchase records. Each customer had one or more behavior tags. Products were recommended according to the customer behavior tag in the recommendation order: products with external tags, new products not purchased previously by the customer, new products purchased previously by the customer, and currently recommended products. The system uses the click rate, recommendation success rate and the turnover of toys as performance indicators.

Experimental Setup and Results

Establishment of the Image Recognition Model

A CNN was used to establish the image recognition model. Keras in Python TensorFlow (a deep learning framework that can support many algorithms) was used to learn. The model was established using the following six steps.

- (1) Select the model architecture. This study utilized a sequential model, which is a straightforward structural framework. It consists of a linear stack of multiple network layers arranged sequentially from start to finish, without any branching paths.
- (2) Construct the network layer. The function variables of the input layer included Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Dropout, and Flatten. The description for each variable is shown below. The functional variable of the output layer was Dense.

- (3) Select the loss function. Binary_crossentropy was used as the loss function. When manually tagging, if the product image contained this type of tag, it was marked as 1; if there was no such feature, it was marked as 0.
- (4) Establish the training model.
 - Establish recognition models for film peripheral goods tags, cartoon peripheral goods tags, and original product tags. The e-commerce platform offers 3,132 kinds of toys; 30 products at a time were used for tag recognition. For tags with less than 95% recognition accuracy, manual calibration was performed until the recognition accuracy of all tags exceeded 95%.
 - Establish the recognition model of product images. As noted earlier, 80% of the images were used for training and 20% for prediction. The number of training models was set to 1,000, and a similarity comparison of product images performed first. Three models (product source, product feature, and product type) were used for training and testing the recognition models of film peripheral goods tags, cartoon peripheral goods tags, and original product tags.
- (5) Verify and compare images.
 - Verify product tag accuracy. In the first verification, 30 products—four film peripheral goods, 14 cartoon peripheral goods and 12 original products—were taken. The accuracy test was repeated 10 times, producing accuracy rates of 73%, 94% and 95% for the three tag types respectively. The eight categories of product feature tags and 12 categories of product type tags were verified 10 times. Tags with less than 95% recognition accuracy were calibrated manually. The first set of recognition accuracy rates of various tags is shown in [Table 2](#).
 - Compare product images. Of the total of 26,882 images 21,506 were randomly selected for training and the remaining 5,376 images used for tests. The processes and steps of product recognition accuracy comparison are shown in [Figure 5](#).

Table 2. Product label image recognition first test results.

Product source (A) 91%(274/300)	Film peripheral goods (A1) 73%(29/40)	Cartoon peripheral goods (A2) 94%(131/140)	Original products (A3) 95%(114/120)
Product feature (B) 75%(226/300)	Animal (B1) 83%(83/100)	Character (B2) 95%(38/40)	Food (B3) 63%(19/30)
	Vehicles (B4) 50%(10/20)	Shooting Tools (B5) 100%(20/20)	Musical instruments (B6) 80%(16/20)
	Scenes (B7) 30%(6/20)	Tools (B8) 68%(34/50)	
	Assembly model (C1) 85%(17/20)	Model (C2) 80%(32/40)	Building blocks (C3) 65%(26/40)
Product type (C) 78%(235/300)	Capsule toys (C4) 80%(16/20)	Educational toys (C5) 25%(5/20)	Action figures (C6) 83%(25/30)
	Dolls (C7) 100%(30/30)	Jigsaw puzzles (C8) 90%(18/20)	Clay (C9) 65%(13/20)
	Play house toys (C10) 85%(17/20)	Pendants (C11) 85%(17/20)	Accessories (C12) 95%(19/20)

Figure 5. Similarity comparison of the product image recognition models.

Tags of film peripheral goods (A1), cartoon peripheral goods (A2), animals (B1), food (B3), vehicles (B4), musical instruments (B6), scenes (B7), tools (B8), assembly models (C1), models (C2), building blocks (C3), capsule toys (C4), educational toys (C5), action figures (C6), jigsaw puzzles (C8), clay (C9), house toys (C10) and pendants (C11) were calibrated manually. Then, another 30 products were taken for tag recognition, totaling 60 products. The results of the second tag recognition process are shown in Table 3. The tag recognition model was trained 19 times on 570 products, accounting for 18.2% (420/3,132) of the total number of products. All tag recognition rates exceeded 95%. The model was then used on the remaining 2,632 products for tag recognition, significantly reducing the cost and time of manual tagging.

Table 3. Product label image recognition second test results.

Product source (A) 93%(558/600)	Film peripheral goods (A1) 79%(63/80)	Cartoon peripheral goods (A2) 95%(265/280)	Original products (A3) 96%(230/240)
Product feature (B) 82%(492/600)	Animal (B1) 86%(171/200)	Character (B2) 98%(78/80)	Food (B3) 70%(42/60)
	Vehicles (B4) 62%(25/40)	Shooting Tools (B5) 100%(40/40)	Musical instruments (B6) 83%(33/40)
	Scenes (B7) 48%(19/40)	Tools (B8) 84%(84/100)	
	Assembly model (C1) 88%(35/40)	Model (C2) 93%(74/80)	Building blocks (C3) 76%(61/80)
Product type (C) 86%(516/600)	Capsule toys (C4) 88%(35/40)	Educational toys (C5) 45%(18/40)	Action figures (C6) 92%(55/60)
	Dolls (C7) 100%(60/60)	Jigsaw puzzles (C8) 95%(38/40)	Clay (C9) 78%(31/40)
	Play house toys (C10) 88%(35/40)	Pendants (C11) 90%(36/40)	Accessories (C12) 95%(38/40)

(6) Order of product recommendation. The customers' purchase records were mined to determine the products purchased, and the tag statistics of those products calculated. Taking the consumption record of Customer 76 as an example, the order of tags was as follows: cartoon peripheral goods (36), character (37), model (32), action [Figures 5](#), original products (1). Combined with the combine trending topics on the internet with toy product that conformed to external tags in the past three months (Jan 1, 2024 to March 29, 2024), products were successfully crawled with the external keywords, and 38 products were not crawled. By changing the keywords into the theme tag, 152 tags were added, making 333 external tags in total. The recommendation order of the tags was as follows: trending topics on the Internet, new products, products not purchased before, and consumer's purchase behavior tags. After the recommendation system was used, the conversion steps of consumers' clicks, views, add to cart, placing orders and payment were recorded, as shown in [Figure 6](#).

Results of Performance Verification of the Dynamic E-Commerce Recommendation System

The authors acquired sales data for the period June 1, 2023 to January 31, 2024 (39 weeks) from a well-known e-commerce platform in Taiwan, and used it in tag definition and training and testing the recognition model. The product recommendation system was updated from March 3, 2024, and customers' views and behavior history recorded until August 17, 2024 (a total of 24 weeks). Compared to the first four weeks (W1–W4), in the last four weeks (W21–W24) the average number of clicks on products in the updated recommendation system was 36.1% higher, the average number of views 22.9% higher, the

Figure 6. Take No.76 consumer’s behavior conversion steps as an example.

Table 4. Statistical table after importing the recommendation system.

Data statistics period	Number of items	average number of clicks	average number of views	the average number of adding to cart	the average number of orders	the average number of payments
W1~W4	3,190	194.022	133.430	7.37	4.37	3.10
W5~W8	3,128	229.046 (18.05%)	140.126 (5.02%)	7.24(-1.83%)	4.51(3.00%)	3.53(13.72%)
W9~W12	3,122	230.074 (18.58%)	153.296 (14.89%)	7.42(0.61%)	4.29(-1.92%)	3.50(12.72%)
W13~W16	3,136	233.511 (20.35%)	155.846 (16.80%)	8.54(15.88%)	4.93(12.68%)	3.82(23.16%)
W17~W20	3,139	251.584 (29.67%)	158.405 (18.72%)	9.21(25.01%)	5.22(19.40%)	3.64(17.15%)
W21~W24	3,131	263.979 (36.06%)	164.003 (22.91%)	9.75(32.29%)	5.61(28.26%)	4.05(30.41%)

average number of products being added to cart was 32.3% higher, the average number of orders 28.3% higher, and the average number of payment transactions 30.41% higher. When the recommendation system aligns more closely with consumers’ expectations and perceptions, it can win consumer’s preference and subsequently drive purchasing behavior. Consumer behavior is described in Table 4.

Conclusions and Management Implications

Research Results

The aim of this study was to use consumer behavior data to create an improved tagging automation and purchase recommendation system for product. The results of the study are summarized below.

Image Recognition Can Solve the Problems of Manual Tagging

Most enterprises that engage in product tagging do so manually, which is time-consuming and subjective. This study established an image recognition model based on a CNN. After 19 iterations of tag recognition training on 570 products, its product tag recognition accuracy exceeded 95%. When the recognition accuracy of product images exceeds 90%, automatic tagging of products can be achieved through image recognition.

Python Web Crawlers Can Contribute to a Dynamic Recommendation System

In the past, most recommendation systems were based on customers' search, browsing, and purchase records. In this study, Python web crawlers were used to crawl Google Trends for keywords discussed within the last three months. Ninety-four products were successfully crawled with the external keywords and 152 tags were added. Hence, we conclude that adding trending topics related to products to a recommendation system makes it dynamic. The products can be tagged to capture customer behavior and form a product recommendation system.

In this study, customers' purchase records were used to tag commercial products. Analysis of the customers' product tag statistics enabled products to be recommended to the consumer according to the following recommendation order: trending topics on the Internet, new products, products not purchased before, and consumer's purchase behavior tags.

Managerial Implications

Capturing Consumer Behavior

During and after the COVID-19 pandemic, the usage rate of e-commerce platforms increased significantly and customer journeys grew increasingly fragmented. Consumers increasingly value privacy in their online purchases, making their behavior difficult to capture. In this study, a product recommendation system based on product tagging was used to capture consumer behavior. As long as the customer purchase record and the automatic recognition ability of product tags are available, a two-way product recommendation system can be established.

Recommending New Products

In the past, new products could not be recommended to customers due to lack of sales records. However, if new products are tagged, they can be recommended to customers with the corresponding tag.

(3) Avoiding slow and costly manual tagging

In this study, an image recognition model was established using a CNN, enabling automatic allocation of product tags.

Creating a Dynamic Product Recommendation System

Most e-commerce product recommendation systems present recommendations based on records of customers' previous purchases, as well as customers' search and browsing records. In this study, trending topics related to products are entered into the recommendation system, enabling it to update itself and generate dynamic tags.

Strengths

Integrating external dynamic tags from Google Trends ensures the recommendation system remains relevant to real-time consumer interests and evolving market trends. Using CNNs for image recognition eliminates the need for labor-intensive manual tagging, reducing costs, time, and the cognitive biases often associated with human annotation. By combining internal features (historical consumer behavior) and external tags (Internet trends), the system accurately aligns recommendations with consumer expectations. Finally, the system mitigates the cold start problem of traditional collaborative filtering systems by integrating dynamic external data to provide meaningful recommendations for new products.

Weaknesses

The system outlined herein relies on Google Trends and web crawlers for external tagging; hence, changes in API policies or data availability could reduce its performance. While the system solves the cold start issue, its reliance on consumer purchase history for internal tagging means it might struggle in cases of extremely sparse user behavior data.

Acknowledgements

The authors have no acknowledgments to declare.

Disclosure Statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This research received no external funding.

ORCID

Wen-Lung Tsai <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7005-3923>

Data Availability Statement

The code of this research is available online (at <https://github.com/OuTsungYin/SDDALab/blob/main/DRSystem-DL>).

References

- Alamdari, P. M., N. J. Navimipour, M. Hosseinzadeh, A. A. Safaei, and A. Darwesh. 2020. A systematic study on the recommender systems in the E-commerce. *Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Access* 8:115694–716. doi:10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3002803.
- Arratia, A., and E. Sepúlveda. 2020. Convolutional neural networks, image recognition and financial time series forecasting. In *Mining data for financial applications. MIDAS 2019. Lecture notes in computer science*, ed. V. Bitetta, I. Bordino, A. Ferretti, F. Gullo, S. Pascolutti, and G. Ponti, 11985. Cham: Springer. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-37720-5_5.
- Breese, J. S., D. Heckerman, and C. Kadie. 2013. Empirical analysis of predictive algorithms for collaborative filtering. arXiv preprint arXiv:1301.7363. doi:10.48550/arXiv.1301.7363.
- Broeder, P., and M. Schouten. 2022. The impact of product tagging on trust and purchase intention: A cross-cultural perspective in visual e-commerce. *CBR - Consumer Behavior Review* 6 (1):1–17. doi:10.51359/2526-7884.2022.250595.
- Chandra, S., S. Verma, W. M. Lim, S. Kumar, and N. Donthu. 2022. Personalization in personalized marketing: Trends and ways forward. *Psychology & Marketing* 39 (8):1529–62. doi:10.1002/mar.21670.
- Chang, M. K., W. Cheung, and M. Tang. 2013. Building trust online: Interactions among trust building mechanisms. *Information & Management* 50 (7):439–45. doi:10.1016/j.im.2013.06.003.
- Chumnumpan, P., and X. Shi. 2019. Understanding new products' market performance using google trends. *Australasian Marketing Journal* 27 (2):91–103. doi:10.1016/j.ausmj.2019.01.001.
- Deldjoo, Y., M. Schedl, P. Cremonesi, and G. Pasi. 2020. Recommender systems leveraging multimedia content. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)* 53 (5):1–38. doi: 10.1145/3407190.
- Ghabayen, A. S., and S. M. Noah. 2017. Using tags for measuring the semantic similarity of users to enhance collaborative filtering recommender systems. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology* 7 (6):2063–70. doi: 10.18517/ijaseit.7.6.1826.
- Grandhi, B., N. Patwa, and K. Saleem. 2021. Data-driven marketing for growth and profitability. *EuroMed Journal of Business* 16 (4):381–98. doi:10.1108/EMJB-09-2018-0054.
- Gu, J., Z. Wang, J. Kuen, L. Ma, A. Shahroudy, B. Shuai, T. Liu, X. Wang, G. Wang, J. Cai, et al. 2018. Recent advances in convolutional neural networks. *Pattern Recognition* 77:354–77. doi: 10.1016/j.patcog.2017.10.013.
- Höpken, W., T. Eberle, M. Fuchs, and M. Lexhagen. 2021. Improving tourist arrival prediction: A big data and artificial neural network approach. *Journal of Travel Research* 60 (5):998–1017. doi:10.1177/0047287520921244.

- Hu, L., K. Lin, M. M. Hassan, A. Alamri, and A. Alelaiwi. 2015. CFSF: On cloud-based recommendation for large-scale e-commerce. *Mobile Networks & Applications* 20 (3):380–90. doi:10.1007/s11036-014-0560-5.
- Hui, S., L. Pengyu, and Z. Kai. 2011. Improving item-based collaborative filtering recommendation system with tag. *2011 2nd International Conference on Artificial Intelligence, Management Science and Electronic Commerce (AIMSEC)*, 2142–45. IEEE. doi: 10.1109/AIMSEC.2011.6011048.
- Jun, S. P., H. S. Yoo, and S. Choi. 2018. Ten Years of research change using google trends: From the perspective of big data utilizations and applications. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change* 130:69–87. doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2017.11.009.
- Katiyar, A., V. Srividya, and B. K. Tripathy. 2021. TagIT: A system for image auto-tagging and clustering. In *Data engineering and intelligent computing. Advances in intelligent systems and computing*, ed. V. Bhateja, S. C. Satapathy, C. M. Travieso-González, and V. N. M. Aradhya, 1407. Singapore: Springer. doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-0171-2_25.
- Kejriwal, M., K. Shen, C. C. Ni, and N. Torzec. 2021. An evaluation and annotation methodology for product category matching in e-commerce. *Computers in Industry* 131:103497. doi:10.1016/j.compind.2021.103497.
- Khatter, H., A. Sharma, and A. K. Kushwaha. 2022. Web scraping based product comparison model for e-commerce websites. *2022 IEEE International Conference on Data Science and Information System (ICDSIS)*, 1–6. IEEE. doi: 10.1109/ICDSIS55133.2022.9915892.
- Khder, M. A. 2021. Web scraping or web crawling: State of art, techniques, approaches and application. *International Journal of Advances in Soft Computing and Its Applications* 13 (3):145–68. doi:10.15849/IJASCA.211128.11.
- Kingma, D. P. 2014. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. arXiv:1412.6980. doi:10.48550/arXiv.1412.6980.
- LeCun, Y., L. Bottou, Y. Bengio, and P. Haffner. 1998. Gradient-based learning applied to document recognition. *Proceedings of the IEEE* 86 (11):2278–324. doi:10.1109/5.726791.
- Li, J., Z. Dou, Y. Zhu, X. Zuo, and J. R. Wen. 2020. Deep cross-platform product matching in e-commerce. *Information Retrieval Journal* 23 (2):136–58. doi: 10.1007/s10791-019-09360-1.
- Li, X., Q. Li, and J. Kim. 2023. A review helpfulness modeling mechanism for online e-commerce: Multi-channel CNN end-to-end approach. *Applied Artificial Intelligence* 37 (1):2166226. doi: 10.1080/08839514.2023.2166226.
- Liao, S. H., R. Widowati, and H. Y. Chang. 2021. A data mining approach for developing online streaming recommendations. *Applied Artificial Intelligence* 35 (15):2204–27. doi:10.1080/08839514.2021.1997211.
- Linden, G., B. Smith, and J. York. 2003. Amazon.com recommendations: Item-to-item collaborative filtering. *IEEE Internet Computing* 7 (1):76–80. doi:10.1109/MIC.2003.1167344.
- Melville, P., R. J. Mooney, and R. Nagarajan. 2002. Content-boosted collaborative filtering for improved recommendations. *AAAI/IAAI* 23:187–92.
- Miklosik, A., M. Kuchta, and S. Zak. 2018. Monetising content through delivery of advertisements: The case of ad blockers. *Ad Alta: Journal of Interdisciplinary Research* 8 (1):175–79.
- Natarajan, S., S. Vairavasundaram, S. Natarajan, and A. H. Gandomi. 2020. Resolving data sparsity and cold start problem in collaborative filtering recommender system using linked open data. *Expert Systems with Applications* 149:113248. doi:10.1016/j.eswa.2020.113248.
- Nwankpa, C. E. 2020. Advances in optimisation algorithms and techniques for deep learning. *Advances in Science Technology and Engineering Systems Journal* 5 (5):563–77. doi:10.25046/aj050570.
- Okwu, E., P. Adewole, and O. Sennaik. 2019. Experimental comparison of stochastic optimizers in deep learning. *Computational Science and Its Applications-ICCSA* 2019:704–15. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-24308-1_55.

- Oltman, J., and J. Zabin. 2002. *Precision marketing: More science than fiction*. London: Sterling Publications.
- Oskooei, A. R., A. Terim, C. Arık, and E. Bıçakçı. 2023. Design and development of an automated product categorization software: Ai-driven solutions for e-commerce platforms. *Orclever Proceedings of Research and Development* 3 (1):367–77. doi:10.56038/oprd.v3i1.399.
- Pan, H., and H. Zhou. 2020. Study on convolutional neural network and its application in data mining and sales forecasting for E-commerce. *Electronic Commerce Research* 20 (2):297–320. doi:10.1007/s10660-020-09409-0.
- Persson, E. 2019. *Evaluating tools and techniques for web scraping*. diss. <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kth:diva-271206>.
- Reyad, M., A. Sarhan, and M. Arafa. 2023. A modified Adam algorithm for deep neural network optimization. *Neural Computing & Applications* 35 (23):17095–112. doi: 10.1007/s00521-023-08568-z.
- Sharma, A., and M. O. Shafiq. 2022. A comprehensive artificial intelligence based user intention assessment model from online reviews and social media. *Applied Artificial Intelligence* 36 (1):2014193. doi:10.1080/08839514.2021.2014193.
- Shimaoka, A. M., R. C. Ferreira, and A. Goldman. 2024. The evolution of CRISP-DM for data science: Methods, processes and frameworks. *SBC Reviews on Computer Science* 4 (1):28–43. doi:10.5753/reviews.2024.3757.
- Skenderi, G., C. Joppi, M. Denitto, and M. Cristani. 2024. Well googled is half done: Multimodal forecasting of new fashion product sales with image-based google trends. *Journal of Forecasting* 43 (6):1982–97. doi:10.1002/for.3104.
- Sulthana, A. R., M. Gupta, S. Subramanian, and S. Mirza. 2020. Retracted article: Improvising the performance of image-based recommendation system using convolution neural networks and deep learning. *Soft Computing* 24 (19):14531–44. doi:10.1007/s00500-020-04803-0.
- Tettamanzi, A. G., M. Carlesi, L. Pannese, and M. Santalmasi. 2007. Business intelligence for strategic marketing: Predictive modelling of customer behaviour using fuzzy logic and evolutionary algorithms. *Proceedings, Applications of Evolutionary Computing: EvoWorkshops 2007: EvoCoMnet, EvoFIN, EvoIASP, EvoINTERACTION, EvoMUSART, EvoSTOC and EvoTransLog*, 233–40. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer. doi: 10.1007/978-3-540-71805-5_26.
- Wang, H.-C., A. Justitia, and C.-W. Wang. 2024. AsCDPR: A novel framework for ratings and personalized preference hotel recommendation using cross-domain and aspect-based features. *Data Technologies and Applications* 58 (2):293–317. doi:10.1108/DTA-03-2023-0101.
- Wang, S., and J. Qiu. 2021. A deep neural network model for fashion collocation recommendation using side information in e-commerce. *Applied Soft Computing* 110:107753. doi:10.1016/j.asoc.2021.107753.
- Wang, Z. 2023. Intelligent recommendation model of tourist places based on collaborative filtering and user preferences. *Applied Artificial Intelligence* 37 (1):2203574. doi:10.1080/08839514.2023.2203574.
- Wedel, M., and P. K. Kannan. 2016. Marketing analytics for data-rich environments. *Journal of Marketing* 80 (6):97–121. doi:10.1509/jm.15.0413.
- Wei, Z., H. Wang, Q. Xu, Y. Qu, and W. Xing. 2024. Optimized attention enhanced temporal graph convolutional network espoused research of intelligent customer service system based on natural language processing technology. *Applied Artificial Intelligence* 38 (1). doi: 10.1080/08839514.2024.2327867.
- Wen, C. H., C. C. Cheng, and Y. C. Shih. 2022. Artificial intelligence technologies for more flexible recommendation in uniforms. *Data Technologies and Applications* 56 (4):626–43. doi:10.1108/DTA-09-2021-0230.

- Wirth, R., and J. Hipp. 2000. CRISP-DM: Towards a standard process model for data mining. *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on the Practical Applications of Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining* 1:29–39.
- Wyner, G. A. 2001. When 360 degrees is not enough. *Marketing Management* 10 (2):4–5. <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/when-360-degrees-is-not-enough/docview/194196690/se-2>.
- Xiao, J., M. Wang, B. Jiang, and J. Li. 2018. A personalized recommendation system with combinational algorithm for online learning. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing* 9 (3):667–77. doi:10.1007/s12652-017-0466-8.
- Xu, K., H. Zhou, H. Zheng, M. Zhu, and Q. Xin. 2024. Intelligent classification and personalized recommendation of e-commerce products based on machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2403.19345*. doi:10.48550/arXiv.2403.19345.
- Yakubu, H., and C. K. Kwong. 2021. Forecasting the importance of product attributes using online customer reviews and google trends. *Technological Forecasting & Social Change* 171:120983. doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2021.120983.
- Yang, Y., B. Guo, Z. Yu, and H. He. 2013. Social activity recognition and recommendation based on mobile sound sensing. *2013 IEEE 10th International Conference on Ubiquitous Intelligence and Computing and 2013 IEEE 10th International Conference on Autonomic and Trusted Computing*, 103–10. doi: 10.1109/UIC-ATC.2013.61.
- Zhen, Y., W. J. Li, and D. Y. Yeung. 2009. TagiCoFi: Tag informed collaborative filtering. *Proceedings of the Third ACM Conference on Recommender Systems*, 69–76. doi: 10.1145/1639714.1639727.